

A FINITE ELEMENT MODEL FOR ANALYSIS OF MULTIPHASE COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper is presented a general *mixing theory* applied to the numerical simulation of multiphase composite material behaviour. This theory is based on the mixture of the basic substances of the composite and allow evaluate the inter-dependence behaviour between the different compounding constitutive models for n-phases composite materials. Also, the initial anisotropy of each compounding is treated in the present work by mean of a *mapped isotropic plastic formulation*. This allows classic isotropic plasticity theory to be applied to orthotropic or anisotropic materials. Examples of application shows the good performance of the mixing anisotropy theory for the simulation of bulk composite materials.

1. INTRODUCTION.

In this paper a constitutive model adequate for analysis of the mechanical response of composite materials is presented. The model is based in the mixture of the basic substances of the composite and allows to evaluate the inter-dependence between the constitutive behaviour of the different compounding materials. The behavior of the each compound is modelled by a general anisotropic elasto-plastic model, termed "base model". The different base models for each compound are combined using mixing theory to simulate the behaviour of the multiphase material.

Mixing theory is based in the principle of interaction of the compounding substances and makes use the following assumptions: a) each infinitesimal volume of a composite is filled by a finite number of compounding substances; b) each compounding substance participates in the behavior of the total composite material in the same volume proportion of the total one; c) all compounding substances have the same strains (compatibility concept); and d) the volume occupied by each compounding substances is much smaller than the total volume of the composite. Assumption (b) implies an homogeneous distribution of all substances in a certain region of the composite. The interaction between the different compounding substances, yields the overall constitutive behavior of the composite ^{4,14,15}.

In this paper mixing theory is used to propose a implicit non linear constitutive model for n-phase composite materials. Each phase can have an anisotropic or isotropic behaviour. The anisotropic behaviour is formulated by means of a *fictional isotropic stress tensor* which results from a fourth order tensor transformation of the real stress to an *homonymous stress space* ^{1,2,3,12}. This allows to use the same yield and potential functions derived for standard isotropic materials, whereas all the relevant information on the material anisotropy properties is embedded in the

fourth order transformation tensor only. The material parameters involved in this tensor can be defined from adequate experimental tests. The formulation presented is completely general and allows to model different class of orthotropic and anisotropic materials typical of composites. The model seems to be particularly suited to be applied for analysis of multiphase materials such as fiber reinforced composites and concrete.

The layout of the paper is the following. In next section the anisotropic elasto-plastic model for each of the individual compounding substances is briefly presented. Then a description of mixing theory used to reproduce the overall behavior of the composite is given. Finally, some examples of application are presented.

2. PLASTIC LAW FOR BASE ANISOTROPIC MATERIALS.

In this section an anisotropic constitutive model for each of compounding substances of a n -phase composite material is presented. The model is formulated in a material configuration using a Total Lagrangean Kinematics and it can deal with non linear problems involving large plastic strains and small elastic strains ^{5,7,8}.

2.1 Yield and potential functions. Space transformation tensor.

It will be assumed that both yield and plastic potential functions are defined in the Piola-Kirchoff stress space (material configuration), as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Yield function: } \mathcal{F}^S(S_{ij}; \theta; \alpha_S^m) &= 0 \\ \text{Potential function: } \mathcal{G}^S(S_{ij}; \theta; \alpha_S^m) &= \kappa \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $S_{ij} = S_{ij}(C_{rs}; \alpha_S^m)$ is the second Piola-Kirchoff stress tensor, $C_{ij} = F_{i*}^T F_{*j}$ is the right Cauchy-Green tensor, F_{ij} is the deformation gradient, α_S^m is a set of m internal plastic variables, κ is a constant parameter, and θ is the temperature free variable.

Traditional procedures for deriving the constitutive equations for anisotropic elasto-plastic materials are based on the description of appropriate yield and potential functions in terms of the characteristic material properties ^{8,10,12}. Satisfaction of the invariance condition in these cases is difficult and not always possible. A procedure to guarantee this condition proposed in this work is to define the properties of the real anisotropic solid in terms of a *fictitious isotropic solid* ^{1,2}. This is achieved by relating the stresses between the *real* and *fictitious* spaces using the following linear transformation (see Figure 1):

$$\tau_{ij} = A_{ijkl} S_{kl} \quad (2)$$

where τ_{ij} and S_{ij} are the stress tensor in the real anisotropic solid and the fictitious isotropic solid, respectively and A_{ijkl} is a fourth order material tensor, termed *space transformation tensor*, whose possible definition, among others, can be the following:

$$A_{ijkl} = c^{\tau}_{ijrs}(\theta) c^{S^{-1}}_{rskl}(\theta) = f_{ik}^{\tau}(\theta) f_{jl}^{S^{-1}}(\theta) \quad (3)$$

where f_{ij}^S , f_{ij}^{τ} are the elastic limit tensors corresponding to the real and fictitious solids respectively and $c^{S^{-1}}_{ijkl}$, c^{τ}_{ijkl} are the constitutive tensors of the real and fictitious solids respectively.

The mapping expressed by eq. (2), produces a change in the yield function shape as it can be seen in Figure 1. In Figure 2, shows this change shape effect for different strength ratios (τ_{ii}/S_{ii}) on same yield functions ^{9,10}: A) Von-Mises, B) Mohr-Coulomb, C) Drucker-Prager, and D) Lubliner-Oller ⁹ for geomaterials. This space mapping also allows the representation of the unidirectional fiber yield function when the ratio ($\tau_{ii}/S_{ii} \rightarrow \infty$) tends to infinity.

Figure 1: Relationship between the real (anisotropic) space(a) and the fictitious (isotropic) space(b).

Figure 2: Change shape effect for different strength ratio (\$\tau_{ii}/S_{ii}\$) on several yield functions: A) Von-Mises, B) Mohr-Coulomb, C) Drucker-Prager, and D) Lubliner-Oller.

Assumed that all the information concerning material anisotropy is contained in tensor \$A_{ijkl}\$. The yield and plastic potential functions for the anisotropic solid are thus defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}^S(S_{ij}; \theta; \alpha_S^m) &= \mathcal{F}^T(S_{ij}; A_{ijkl}; \theta; \alpha_r^m) = \mathcal{F}^T(\tau_{ij}; \theta; \alpha_r^m) = 0 \\ g^S(S_{ij}; \theta; \alpha_S^m) &= g^T(S_{ij}; A_{ijkl}; \theta; \alpha_r^m) = g^T(\tau_{ij}; \theta; \alpha_r^m) = \kappa \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

In following sections the main relationships characterizing an anisotropic elasto-plastic solid formulated by means of the space transformation are derived.

2.2 Secant constitutive equation. Flow rule and internal variables.

The constitutive equation is obtained by writing the dissipation occurring in an elastoplastic process in the real anisotropic space. From the standard thermodynamic theory, the secant

constitutive equation is obtained as ^{7,8,10,12,15}:

$$S_{ij} = m^0 \frac{\partial \Psi^S(E_{ij}^e; \theta; \alpha_S^m)}{\partial E_{ij}^e} = A_{ijkl}^{-1} c_{klrs}^r(\theta) E_{rs}^e = A_{ijkl}^{-1} \tau_{kl} \quad (5)$$

where τ_{ij} are the stresses in the fictitious isotropic space and Ψ^S is the free energy formulated in the material configuration under real stress state ¹².

From eqs. (2) and (4) the flow rule and the evolution of the internal plastic variables α_S^m are obtained in the form

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{E}_{ij}^p &= \dot{\lambda} \frac{\partial g^S}{\partial S_{ij}} = \dot{\lambda} \frac{\partial g^r}{\partial \tau_{kl}} \frac{\partial \tau_{kl}}{\partial S_{ij}} = \dot{\lambda} \underbrace{\frac{\partial g^r}{\partial \tau_{kl}} A_{klij}}_{R_{ij}^S} = (\dot{E}_{kl}^p)^r A_{klij} \\ \dot{\alpha}_S^m &= \dot{\lambda} (h_{ij}^m)_S \frac{\partial g^S}{\partial S_{ij}} = \dot{\lambda} (h_{ij}^m)_S \frac{\partial g^r}{\partial \tau_{kl}} \frac{\partial \tau_{kl}}{\partial S_{ij}} = \dot{\lambda} (h_{ij}^m)_S \underbrace{\frac{\partial g^r}{\partial \tau_{kl}} A_{klij}}_{R_{ij}^S} = \dot{\lambda} (h_{kl}^m)_r \underbrace{\frac{\partial g^r}{\partial \tau_{kl}}}_{R_{kl}^r} = \dot{\alpha}_r^m \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Figure 3: Plastic flow change effect between real ($r = 1$) and fictitious spaces ($r = 4.5$).

where $(h_{ij}^m)_S$ and $(h_{ij}^m)_r$ are a tensorial functions to be determined ⁹ for each one of the

“ m ” internal variables involved, and $(\dot{E}_{kl}^p)^r$ is the fictitious plastic strain defined in the ideal isotropic space, as is shown in Figure 3. It is possible to proof that the elastic Green-Naghdi strain E_{ij}^e is unique in both spaces ¹².

2.3 Tangent constitutive equation.

The rate form of the constitutive equation is obtained by performing the temporal derivatives of the secant expression (5) as:

$$\dot{S}_{ij} = \frac{\partial S_{ij}}{\partial E_{kl}^e} \dot{E}_{kl}^e + \frac{\partial S_{ij}}{\partial \theta} \dot{\theta} = A_{ijkl}^{-1} c_{klrs}^r(\theta) \underbrace{(\dot{E}_{rs}^e - \dot{E}_{rs}^p)}_{\dot{\tau}_{kl}} - A_{ijrs}^{-1} \underbrace{\bar{\beta}_{rs}^\theta}_{\dot{\tau}_{rs}^\theta} \dot{\theta} \quad (7)$$

$\dot{\tau}_{rs}^\theta = c_{rsnm}^r \dot{E}_{nm}^e$

The plastic consistency condition leads to the standard rate form of the constitutive equation in the fictitious isotropic space as:

$$\dot{\tau}_{ij} = C_{ijkl}^{\tau ep} \dot{E}_{kl} - C_{ijkl}^{\tau \theta} \dot{E}_{kl}^{\theta} \quad (8)$$

where $C_{ijkl}^{\tau ep}$ and $C_{ijkl}^{\tau \theta}$ are the elastic-plastic and thermal constitutive tangent tensors. Details of its mathematics form can be found in ^{11,12}.

Substituting now (8) in (7) leads to the final expression of the rate constitutive equation in the real anisotropic solid as:

$$\dot{S}_{ij} = A_{ijkl}^{-1} \dot{\tau}_{kl} = \underbrace{A_{ijkl}^{-1} C_{klrs}^{\tau ep}}_{C_{ijrs}^{S ep}} \dot{E}_{rs} - \underbrace{A_{ijkl}^{-1} C_{klrs}^{\tau \theta}}_{C_{ijrs}^{S \theta}} \dot{E}_{rs}^{\theta} \quad (9)$$

Above definitions allow to derive all the basic constitutive relationships, necessary to formulate the behaviour of an anisotropic elasto-plastic solid.

3. CONSTITUTIVE MODEL BASED ON MIXING THEORY.

In this section a theory for *interaction* of compounding substances ^{4,11,14,15} of a multiphase material based on local continuum mechanics is presented. This allows to consider the simultaneous combination of the different constitutive behaviour of each substances (i.e.: elastic, elasto-plastic, elasto-brittle elasto-damage, etc.). In this paper each compounding substance behaves precisely as the anisotropic elasto-plastic material previously described. However, other constitutive combinations are obviously possible.

Mixing theory is based on the assumption that, if the atomic diffusions is neglected (i.e.: *temperatures are moderate*) the compounding strain compatibility is satisfied. Moreover, in composite materials the free energy can be written as (see Trusdell and Toupin ¹⁵)

$$m^0 \Psi^S(E_{ij}^e; \theta; \alpha^m) = m^0 \Psi^S(E_{ij}; \theta; \underbrace{E_{ij}^p; \alpha^m}_{p_s}) = m^0 \sum_{c=1}^n k_c \Psi_c^S(E_{ij}; \theta; (p_s)_c) \quad (11)$$

where $\Psi_c^S(E_{ij}; \theta; (p_s)_c)$ is the free energy corresponding to each of the n^{th} compounding substances involved in the mixture, $k_c = dV_c/dV$ is the volume fraction of that substance, $(p_s)_c$ is a set of the inner variables for the "c" compounding and θ is the free thermal variable. Note that the summation over all volume fraction participation should be equal one, which implies that for single phase materials the free energy expression is recovered.

Following an identical procedure to single-phase materials (see section 2) ^{7,9,13}, the expression for the secant and tangent constitutive equation as well as the thermal dilatancy tensor of composite are obtained from Clasius-Planck ^{7,8,10} inequality as:

$$S_{ij} = m^0 \frac{\partial \Psi^S(E_{pq}; \theta; p_r)}{\partial E_{ij}} = m^0 \sum_{c=1}^n k_c \frac{\partial \Psi_c^S(E_{pq}; \theta; (p_r)_c)}{\partial E_{ij}} = \sum_{c=1}^n k_c (S_{ij})_c \quad (11a)$$

$$C_{ijkl}^S = m^0 \frac{\partial^2 \Psi^S(E_{pq}; \theta; p_r)}{\partial E_{ij} \partial E_{kl}} = m^0 \sum_{c=1}^n k_c \frac{\partial^2 \Psi_c^S(E_{pq}; \theta; (p_r)_c)}{\partial E_{ij} \partial E_{kl}} = \sum_{c=1}^n k_c (C_{ijkl}^S)_c \quad (11b)$$

$$\bar{\alpha}_{ij}^\theta = -m^0 \frac{\partial^2 \Psi^S(E_{pq}; \theta; p_r)}{\partial S_{ij} \partial \theta} = -m^0 \sum_{c=1}^n k_c \frac{\partial^2 \Psi_c^S(E_{pq}; \theta; (p_r)_c)}{\partial S_{ij} \partial \theta} = \sum_{c=1}^n k_c (\bar{\alpha}_{ij}^\theta)_c \quad (11c)$$

where $(S_{ij})_c$ is the second Piola Kirchoff stress tensor in the c^{th} corresponding substance. Assuming the strains to be additivity ($E_{ij} = E_{ij}^e + E_{ij}^p + E_{ij}^\theta$) in the Green-Naghdi form ⁵, the stress-strain relationship is derived from the strain compatibility condition between substances as:

$$(E_{ij})_c = E_{ij} = \underbrace{(c^{S^{-1}}_{ijkl}(\theta))_c (S_{kl})_c}_{(E_{ij}^e)_c} + (E_{ij}^p)_c + \underbrace{(\bar{\alpha}_{ij}^\theta)_c (\theta - \theta_o)}_{(E_{ij}^\theta)_c} \quad (12)$$

Where θ_o is the room temperature. The secant constitutive equation is obtained as:

$$S_{ij} = \sum_{c=1}^n k_c (S_{ij})_c = \sum_{c=1}^n k_c (c^S_{ijkl}(\theta))_c (E_{kl}^e)_c = c^S_{ijkl}(\theta) E_{kl}^e \quad (13)$$

From the last two members of eq. (13) and taking into account (11b), it is possible to write the total plastic strain for the composite material as:

$$E_{ij}^p = c^{S^{-1}}_{ijpq}(\theta) \left\{ \sum_{c=1}^n k_c (c^S_{pqrs}(\theta))_c [(E_{rs}^p)_c + (\bar{\alpha}_{rs}^\theta)_c (\theta - \theta_o)] \right\} - \bar{\alpha}_{ij}^\theta (\theta - \theta_o) \quad (14)$$

Substituting eq. (11b) in (12) and taking into account eq. (13) and the strain compatibility condition is possible to obtain the stress tensor for each phase as:

$$(S_{ij})_c = [(c^S_{ijpq}(\theta))_c c^{S^{-1}}_{pqkl}(\theta) \sum_{c=1}^n k_c (c^S_{klrs}(\theta))_c [E_{rs}^e + E_{rs}^p]] - (c^S_{ijpq}(\theta))_c [(E_{pq}^p)_c - (\bar{\alpha}_{pq}^\theta)_c (\theta - \theta_o)] \quad (15)$$

Equation (15), gives the stress distribution for each compounding substance of the multiphase composite.

3. EXAMPLES.

3.1 Elastic behaviour of a fiber reinforced composite.

This trivial example shows the capability of the present model for the simulation of elastic behaviour of fiber reinforced composites.

Table 1 - FRACTION OF FIBERS LOAD $P_{Fibers}/P_{Composite}$.

E_F/E_C	$P_F/P_C _{k_F=0.1}$	$P_F/P_C _{k_F=0.2}$	$P_F/P_C _{k_F=0.4}$
0.50	5.26315	11.11111	25.00000
1.00	10.00000	20.00000	40.00000
10.00	52.63157	71.42857	86.95650
40.00	81.63265	90.90909	96.38554
60.00	86.95652	93.75000	97.56097

Table 1 shows the variation of load ratio P_F/P_C , carried by longitudinal fibers and composite, against the Young modular ratio E_F/E_C , for several values of fraction volume fibers k_F . This results can be seen in total agreement with those reported by Jayatilaka ⁶ obtained by means of a simple elastic model for a fiber reinforced composite.

3.2 Orientation effect for unidirectional fibers.

Figure 4: Strength ratio Vs. Fiber slope angle, for hypothetical epoxy matrix with glass fiber.

Let us consider the case where the continuous fibers are placed unidirectionally and from an angle ϕ with the applied tension load as shown in Figure 4. The failure limit depends on the fiber orientation which angle will be varied between $0^\circ < \phi < 90^\circ$. The material properties are the following: Young modulus along principal directions: in-plane directions, $E_{Long.} = 591998.8 \text{ kg/cm}^2$, and $E_{Trans.} = 140617.3 \text{ kg/cm}^2$. Poisson ratio: $\nu_{LT} = 0.293$. Elastic strength limits, in-plane directions: for the longitudinal fiber behaviour $f_{Long}^{Comp.} = 19686.4 \text{ kg/cm}^2$, $f_{Long}^{Tens.} = 9561.9 \text{ kg/cm}^2$, $f_{LT}^{Shear.} = 421.8 \text{ kg/cm}^2$; and for transverse

fiber behaviour $f_{Trans.}^{Comp.} = 1406.2 \text{ kg/cm}^2$, $f_{Trans.}^{Tens.} = 281.2 \text{ kg/cm}^2$.

Additional data required for the anisotropic model proposed are: Equivalent Young modulus: $E^r = 591998.8 \text{ kg/cm}^2$, Equivalent elastic compression strength limit: $f^{tau} = 19686.4 \text{ kg/cm}^2$, Mohr-Coulomb yield function, fiber plastic flow (only has component on the fiber direction) and perfect plasticity.

In this particular case we examine the single tension strength respect to ϕ fiber angle. The response of the material is shown in Figure 4. The maximum strength is produced for $\phi = 0^\circ$ and the minimum for $\phi = 45^\circ$. The material strength is greater for $\phi = 90^\circ$ than $\phi = 45^\circ$ due to the transversal deformation restricted by the compression strength of the fibers.

3.3 Analysis of a Steel reinforced concrete specimen.

The proposed model has also been tested on a simple reinforced concrete specimen under axial loading acting as shows Figure 5. Plane stress condition have been assumed and three kinds of composite material are used as shows in the following:

Composite (a): 100 % of concrete. Plastic fracture behaviour. Mohr-Coulomb yield and potential functions are assumed.

Composite (b): 90 % of concrete + 10 % of steel longitudinal bars. For concrete: Plastic fracture behaviour. Mohr-Coulomb yield and potential functions are assumed. Elastic behaviour has been assumed for the steel bars.

Figure 5: A): Stress-strain curves for composites (a), (b) and (c). B) Stress-strain behaviour for each compounding of the composite (c): curve (1) represent the composite behaviour and curves (2) and (3) the steel and concrete components.

Composite (c): 90 % of concrete + 10 % of steel longitudinal bars. For concrete: Plastic fracture behaviour, and Mohr-Coulomb yield and potential function are assumed. For the steel bars: Perfect Von Mises plasticity are assumed.

Additional properties for the concrete: $E = 395000.0 \text{ kg/cm}^2$, $\nu = 0.24$, $\phi = \psi = 15^\circ$, $f_{Comp} = 229.0 \text{ kg/cm}^2$, $f_{Comp}^{peak} = 328.0 \text{ kg/cm}^2$, $f_{Tens} = 22.9 \text{ kg/cm}^2$, $G_f = 0.16 \text{ kg/cm}$, $G_c = 16.0 \text{ kg/cm}$, $E^{peak} = 0.38 E^{ultimate}$

Additional properties for the steel bars: $E = 2100000.0 \text{ kg/cm}^2$, $\nu = 0.30$, $\phi = \psi = 15^\circ$, $f_{Comp} = f_{Tens} = 1200.0 \text{ kg/cm}^2$.

Figure (5A) shows the stress-strain behaviour curves for the composites (a), (b) and (c). The plastification points was verified by means of a simple plasticity theory. Total agreement with the present model was obtained.

Figure (5B) shows the stress-strain behaviour for each compounding of the composite c). In this Figure, curve 1) represent the composite behaviour and curves 2) and 3) the steel and the concrete components respectively. The apparent small hardening exhibit by the steel is due to the transversal interaction between the concrete and steel. The uniaxial steel strength (1200.0 kg/cm^2) is reached when the concrete response vanish.

3.4 Fracture test for a bulk composite material.

Figure 6: Test specimen. Geometry, boundary conditions, loading and finite element mesh.

Table 2 - PROPERTIES OF COMPOUNDING MATERIALS.

Compon.	E [$\frac{kg}{cm^2}$]	ν	$f^{Comp.}$ [$\frac{kg}{cm^2}$]	G_f [$\frac{kg}{cm}$]	$f_{Peak}^{Comp.}$ [$\frac{kg}{cm^2}$]	$E_{Peak}^{Comp.}$	Vol. [%]
Steel	2.100E6	0.30	2100.0	500.0	2500.0	0.004	40.0
Aluminum	0.725E6	0.25	1100.0	300.0	1500.0	0.004	40.0
Brass	0.800E6	0.20	650.0	200.0	1000.0	0.003	20.0

Figure 7: A) Stress-strain curves: * At the sample center (a,b,c,d) and at the sample end (b',c',d'). B) Detail of the stress-strain curves at sample ends.

Figure 8: a) Final mesh deformation. b) Principal plastic deformation at the end of the numerical test.

This example shows capability of the present theory to model the fracture behaviour. An imposed displacement field is prescribed in the plane rectangular specimen shown in Figure 6. Plane stress condition has been assumed. The geometry has been discretized using a mesh of 16 quadrilateral standard four nodes element. The type and combination of compounding material are reported in table 2.

For each of the three compounding materials, the principal difference in the response are

beyond the post-peak behaviour. It is when the stress-strain curves beginning with the strain-softening behaviour. Figure 7 case A) shows the stress-strain behaviour of the composite and compounding materials. In such Figure, for composite material (curve a) the stress peak is reached at $S = 1768.0 \text{ kg/cm}^2$. Figure 7 case B) shows a detail of Figure 7 case A) about of the unload response of the points located on the sample extreme zone.

Figure 8a shows the strong strain localization effects at the center of the deformed mesh. Also, in Figure 8b we can see the high concentration of plastic strain. This situation can be interpreted as a measure or level of the micro-fracture process occurred in the sample ⁹.

4. CONCLUDING REMARKS.

The formulation presented here provides a powerful tool for modeling the non linear behaviour of composite materials. Moreover, the formulation presented here can simulate the fracture behavior of each component, as well as the localized failure of composite material.

Extension of the anisotropic formulation presented to account non linear damage phenomena as well as to simulate delamination effects are straight forward and are currently investigated by the authors.

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